

D8.3: Promotional Video, first batch

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Revision history:

VERSION	DATE	Revised by	Reason
0.1	05/07/2023	Vana Stavridi, Nicol Sarla, Panagiotis Kavouras	Preparation of the script
0.2	20/07/2023	Rigmor Baraas, Rose bernabe	Comments on the 1st draft of the voice over
0.3	19/09/2023	NTUA team	Preparation of the first version of the video
0.4	28/09/2023	NTUA team	Corrections on the first version of video
0.5.	3/10/2023	NTUA team	Preparation of prefinal version of video
0.6.	25/10/2023	Rigmor Baraas, Rose bernabe	Comments on the prefinal version of video
1.0.	31/10/2023	NTUA team	Release the 1st promotional video

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1. Aim of the 1st promotional video

Within the framework of the dissemination and communication activities for XR4Human in collaboration with coordinators, WP8 worked to develop the 1st promotional video for the project. As set out in the Grant Agreement, the promotional video supports the dissemination and communication effort of the project. It aims to raise awareness of the project. The 1st promotional video presents a summary of the project, its objectives as well as the project main outputs. It mainly targets non-expert audience and captures all basic elements of XR4Human project through pictures of real people and some animations. The video will be made available on the project website and project YouTube channel.

2. Video Design and Format

The videos were crafted in alignment with the distinctive visual identity and branding of XR4Human. We consistently incorporated the project's official colors, fonts, and icons to ensure a cohesive and recognizable look. XR4Human's visual identity, characterized by vibrant colors and imagery related to VR, AR, and XR technologies, was deliberately employed to make the content visually appealing and user-friendly. As a result, the video visuals harmonize with these key elements, maintaining a consistent and engaging aesthetic.

Below it is presented the video by showcasing the voice over and some characteristic screen captures.

LOGO

Scene 1

Script ➡ No voice over

Visual ➡ Gradual appearance of the XR4HUMAN logo in the form of pixels which, as they are composed, will create the complete image of the logo.

*Note: The colors and theme should match those of the XR4Human website (<https://xr4human.eu/>). The transitions between words and graphics should be a bit more interesting than just fading or sliding. More like, popping, growing, shrinking, and moving.

Scene 2

Script → No voice over

Visual

Scene 3

Script

XR4Human is a 3-year EU-funded project with the mission to provide guidance and tools in order to ensure the Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered development of eXtended Reality Technologies

Visual

Scene 4

Script

For such an ambitious mission to be met, XR4Human brings together a multi-national and transdisciplinary consortium, coordinated by the University of South-Eastern Norway.

Visual

Scene 5

Script

The power of eXtended Reality lies in its limitless potential for enhancing human experience. eXtended Reality creates and recreates reality, extends it, and bends it in a manner that was previously restricted to the world of science fiction. Major advances from some of the world's largest companies means that these technologies are now cost-effective enough for businesses and consumers to take advantage of these possibilities, from improving production processes, providing novel learning and training tools, and supporting health and wellbeing.

Visual

Scene 6

Script

As with other emerging technologies, however, the use and eventual ubiquity of eXtended Reality technologies bring with them potential risks that have not existed before.
Of particular importance are the risks associated with Physical and mental health, Diversity, inclusivity, abuse of power, accessibility issues, Privacy, ownership, access, data issues, Interoperability issues, among others.

Visual

Scene 7

Script

Developing the foundations to ensure that Europe is sufficiently equipped to leverage the opportunities of eXtended Reality technologies through skillful navigation of these new challenges is the rationale for XR4HUMAN.

Visual

Scene 9

Script

All the activities of XR4Human revolve around four interconnected and mutually influencing pillars, forming a cohesive and harmonious foundation.

EXPLORE *ethical issues and related regulatory and governance issues*
GUIDE *companies and regulators through an Interoperability Guidance Document; a European Code of Conduct for Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered eXtended Reality Technologies; demonstration of the the practical applications of the eXtended Reality Code of Conduct; AND, for users, through a rating system and educational materials.*

Visual

Scene 9

Script

EQUIP *companies and regulators with an online repository of test cases and users through a rating system and educational materials*

ENGAGE *companies and other stakeholders to enhance the uptake of the eXtended Reality Code of Conduct, the Guidance for Interoperability, and the empowerment of end-users.*

Visual

Scene 10

Script

Stay tuned with XR4Human's progress by following us through our Twitter and LinkedIn accounts, and by visiting the project's website.

Visual

3. Communication of the 1st promotional video

The video will be used a communication and dissemination tool to promote XR4Human project as well as the objectives and the mail outputs. While the other two next promotional videos will promote in details the findings and results of the project. The 1st promotional video will be shared online on the project's website, the XR4Human project YouTube Channel and social media channels. The WP8 will provide all the project partners with the video URL to facilitate the communication of the video through pre-existing networks including partners' social media accounts, etc. In addition, the video can be used at events and conferences (e.g. inserted in presentation or played on laptops/screens) to illustrate the key objectives, procedures and methodology of the project in a more attractive manner.

4. Deviations from DoA

No Deviations from DoA.